

AIMC 2024 (09/09 - 11/09)

der Küchenchef performance at club night

Published on: Aug 29, 2024

URL: <https://aimc2024.pubpub.org/pub/55mwo8er>

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Program Notes

der Küchenchef is an active user of several AI music services, including Boomy and suno. His music often makes references to food, but also experiences in the Berlin rave scene from the 1990s. Of principal importance to *der Küchenchef* is the use of visuals accompanying his music. Boomy described his award-winning 2023 Boomy concept album, “Spätzle, Röstli, Schnitzel, Braten”: “The power of cuisine when shared with a loved one in their final days. *der Küchenchef*’s concept album reflects on the moments they shared with their father, reflecting about life over food from their father’s childhood in Austria.” His most recent album, [“Long time listener, first time whistler”](#) features himself whistling over 21 tracks generated by Boomy while listening to them for the first time. Recently, *der Küchenchef* has been exploring combining Boomy and suno.

Media

Still from the piece [“guten morgAln \(Trüffel, trüffel, trüffel, trüffel\)”](#)

Still from the piece "[ecstAlcy \(Wo bist du?\)](#)"

Here is a video of a performance by der Küchenchef: <https://youtu.be/CTZtHNkD23w>

Ethics statement

der Küchenchef is not an employee of Boomy or suno, and does not possess any financial stake in either company. Hence, there are no financial conflicts of interest to a performance of *der Küchenchef*. The audio-visual performance of *der Küchenchef* in a night club venue does not need to be reviewed by an institutional ethics committee as it does not present dangerous situations, or ethically questionable visuals and sounds. The potential societal, economic and environmental impact of a performance of *der Küchenchef* might include perceived waste of time on the part of listeners, but also enjoyment; the use of energy in powering the computer and AV equipment; and the promotion of anticopyright mentality, where sampling and plunderphonics are normalized.